

**Support Uptake Integrated
Pest Management and Low-
Risk Pesticide Use**

Deliverable: 4.1
Title: Workbook for Multistakeholder engagement

**Horizon Europe Research and Innovation
Programme**

Grant agreement: 101084527
Project duration: 48 months

Published by the SUPPORT consortium Dissemination
level:PUBLIC

Funded by the European Union. Horizon Europe Grant Agreement Nr. 101084527. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Document Control Information

Project Title:	Support Uptake Integrated Pest Management and Low-Risk Pesticide Use
Acronym:	SUPPORT
Project Manager:	Dora Lakner
Scientific Coordinator:	Johan Bremmer

Deliverable	Number	[1]	Title	Workbook for Multistakeholder engagement
Work Package	Number	[4]	Title	SUPPORT Multi stakeholder approach

Document Authors:	Name and organization	Alberto Sturla (CREA PB): Chapters 1 & 2; Paragraphs 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4; 4.9; Clara Sciffer (ILVO): Chapter 3; Simona Cristiano (CREA PB); Paragraphs 4.5 & 4.7; Laura Viganò (CREA PB): Paragraph 4.6; Francesco Licciardo (CREA PB); Paragraph 4.8; Dora Lakner (WUR): Paragraph 4.10	Contact first author:	Alberto Sturla Alberto.sturla@crea.gov.it
Contributors:	Name and organization			

Deliverable type:	R
Dissemination level:	Public
Due date of deliverable:	30/06/2023
Actual submission date:	30/06/2023

This report only reflects the views of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Document Approver(s) and Reviewer(s)

NOTE: All Approvers are required. Records of each approver must be maintained. All Reviewers in the list are considered required unless explicitly listed as Optional.

Name	Role	Action	Date
Johan Bremmer	Scientific Coordinator	Review	23.06.2023
Dora Lakner	Project Manager	Review, contribution to monitoring subchapter	26.06.2023

Document history

The Document Author is authorized to make the following types of changes to the document without requiring that the document be re-approved:

- Editorial, formatting, and spelling
- Clarification

To request a change to this document, contact the Document Author or Owner.

Changes to this document are summarized in the following table in reverse chronological order (latest version first).

Revision	Date	Created by	Short Description of Changes
1	28.06.2023	Albero Sturla	Based on review.

Configuration Management: Document Location

The latest version of this controlled document is stored in:

[SUPPORT_Horizon-CL6-2022-FARM2FORK-01-02socio-economics of pesticide use in agriculture - 1. Deliverables - All Documents \(sharepoint.com\)](#)

Executive summary of the deliverable

The aim of the deliverable is primarily to provide some guidelines for the implementation of SUPPORT multi actor platforms, but its scope could be widened to whoever is engaged in managing participatory processes either in European projects or not, as it adopts a very practical approach to co-creation and knowledge sharing.

The first chapter is devoted to a very hands-on guide on “how to” manage a Focus Group, a research method that brings together a small group of people to answer questions in a moderated setting, it is therefore a most used co-creation tool whenever it comes to ranging different opinions and ideas or when it is needed to explore a problem from different point of views The chapter is designed to answer SUPPORT partners specific needs, but offers a sound overview of organizational issues related to Focus Groups.

Then the second chapter is devoted both to describe the methodological aspects underlying the concept of “community of practice” intended as “a group of people who share a common concern, a set of problems, or an interest in a topic and who come together to fulfil both individual and group goal”. It provides some practical guideline for their organization, maintenance, and facilitation, so to foster participation and a common sense of belonging, towards the fulfilment of SUPPORT Again, the approach is very much “hands on” so to provide ready to use tools for CoP leaders.

Lastly, The Monitoring and Evaluation tool for SUPPORT multi-actor approach is described. It aims at describing the multi-actor initiatives according to the “impact chain”. Although qualitative in nature, the set of indicators that has been elaborated, will be useful in guiding decision making toward a better functioning of the multi-actor platform.

Contents

Executive summary of the deliverable	3
Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms.....	5
1. Introduction	6
2. Actors identification.....	7
3. NCC Focus Groups	1
3.1 Guidelines for effective Organization of Focus Groups	1
4. Community of Practice	4
4.1 Setting up of the CoP	5
4.2 Fostering a shared vision: Appreciative Inquiry	6
4.3 Manage discussion in heterogeneous groups: the double diamond approach.....	9
4.4 What is co-creation?	10
4.5 Methodologies for the conduction of in-person meetings.....	13
4.6 Co-creation and interaction through asynchronous tools.....	18
4.7 Lifecycle of the CoPs	21
4.8 A tool for policy design: relational SWOT.....	22
4.9 Monitoring and evaluation of the multistakeholder approach	24
4.10 The Energy Timeline	27
5. References.....	29

Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AI	Appreciative Inquiry
DD	Double Diamond
CoP	Community of Practices
FG	Focus Group
IPM	Integrated Pest Management
MAA	Multi-Actor Approach
NCC	National Crop Cluster
NoP	Network of Practices

1. Introduction

The scope of this Deliverable 4.1 is to provide SUPPORT project partners with “a handbook” for animating project multi-actor platform. Nevertheless, it adopts a very practical approach to co-creation, that could be extended to the benefit of whoever is working on similar initiatives, also beyond European projects, as it could provide valuable insights to facilitators of a wide range of cooperation initiatives.

Multi Actor Approach (MAA) brings together people from different backgrounds (science, practice...) along with anyone who can help tackle the objective of the project. All experience and knowledge are therefore taken into account and together they concur to create new knowledge for the advancement of the project. The collaboration between all of these different partners also helps to implement results and broadly communicate right from the project start.

European Commission is giving a great importance to MAA in Horizon Cluster 6: 42% of the topics listed in cluster 6 of the 2021-2022 Working Programme are Multifactor, covering 41% of the budget are Multi-actor (Brzezina, 2022).

Despite the relevance attributed to MAA by the European Commission, their effectiveness is hampered by a series of flaws that are inherent to the instrument. For instance the presence of dominant position in multi-actor platforms, sometimes bringing different opinions, also divergent from project objectives, could contribute in failure (Cronin et al., 2022).

In order to prevent such a failure, effective facilitation is key: “A *'participatory method'* per se does not exist because whether or not a method becomes participatory, relies on the frame of mind of the facilitator (Groot, 2002 cited by Macken-Walsh, 2017)

Effective facilitation brings together different people with different stories and *desiderata* and support them in bringing a valuable contribution *according to what they are*, not to the results we are looking for. In order to achieve such a result, facilitation should guarantee that participation of people engaged in multi-actor processes is developed through five elements (Macken-Walsh, A., 2017)

1. **Engaging** and **Incentivising** stakeholders, by demonstrating the relevance and usefulness of SUPPORT events
2. **Interrogating** existing knowledge from experts
3. **Creating** new ideas and knowledge, through co-design and co-creation
4. **Addressing** challenges/problem solving Through new relationships, networks, etc.
5. **Applying** knowledge to particular contexts, scenarios: application

There are specific tools and methodological framework that support facilitation in achieving those five steps of facilitations, and some of them are presented in this deliverable, relying on current practices and the results of other European projects (I2 connect - <https://i2connect-h2020.eu/>, above all). It is a set of instructions that, despite being as specific as possible, they are not intended for being adopted “step by step” in actual practice, although it is surely an option. Rather, their aim is to provide insights that could help understand partners’ role in animating a multi-actor platform in their Country, so to support them in adapting co-creation processes to local specificities.

2. Actors identification

Actors identification is a first and necessary step of each multi-actor process, as it allows to get an overview of all key stakeholders who could get or are involved in and influence your community and at the same time eases their identification according to their roles and positions. For the purposes of SUPPORT four main type of actors have been identified, those that will be actively engaged in the project: for co-creation, for dissemination and communication.

Table 1: Target groups for SUPPORT multi-actor platform

Target Groups	Description
Main IPM actors (TG1, 2, 3 and 4)	Individuals or organisations that have an interest or influence in the project and are affected by its outcomes. They are essentially the (end-) users of the project results who are backed up by any other useful intermediaries and actors who can contribute with further expertise and innovative ideas relevant to the topic's objectives (Scientific community and education (TG1), farmers and their associations (TG2), Advisory Services providers & researchers (TG3), Input suppliers (TG4),). They must be involved in co-creation processes (NCC & CoP).
Policymakers (TG6)	The involvement of policymakers at different levels can help in identifying explicit (i.e. environmental and pesticides legislations.) and implicit policy instruments (i.e. funding programs, tax incentives, priorities for funding opportunities) that need to be strengthened or redefined to support transition toward sustainable IPM practices. Politicians at all levels (from European to local), civil servant in relevant departments (e.g.: Ministry of agriculture, managing authorities), as well lobbyists all fall within this category. They must be involved in dedicated CoPs sessions (WP3).
Citizens and their organisations (TG5)	Citizen & civil society at large involvement can help ensure that research and innovation are relevant to societal needs and values, and that they are aligned with the EU's goals for economic, social, and environmental sustainability. Whenever deemed relevant, they could be involved in CoPs. Their representations (e.g.: consumers associations) must be involved in communication initiatives and in the overarching NoP.
Agri-food supply chain actors (TG5)	They are those who have an interest, also indirect, in IPM practices (e.g.; retailing and processing industries) ¹ . Whenever deemed relevant, they could be involved in CoPs. Their representations (e.g.; retailers associations) must be involved in communication initiatives and in the overarching NoP.

¹ A growing consumers' awareness on food safety has made retailers and processors very sensitive on pesticide residues issues

--	--

In order to cluster actors in a way that is relevant to the project and meaningful for actors themselves, it is necessary to classify them according to the degree of contribution they could give to SUPPORT activities.

The Influence-Interest Matrix is the most common way to do that.

According to this method, actors are gathered in homogeneous groups on the base of their interest or influence on the topic. **Interest** measures to what degree the stakeholder is likely to be affected by the adoption of new IPM strategies and what degree of interest or concern it has in them, while **Influence** measures the power the stakeholder has over the development of new IMP strategies and to what degree it can help achieve or block related vision and objectives.

The positioning of the actors over an I-I continuum is made visually by putting them on a cartesian diagram (fig. 1)

Figure 1: I-I diagram

Source: Authors' elaboration

The involvement in SUPPORT multi-actor activities will be based on the position on the diagram:

- Quadrant I High Influence – Low Interest: They are mostly recipients of Communication and
- Dissemination actions. Could be involved in NCC FGs and in CoPs on interest areas

- Quadrant II High Influence – High Interest: They must be primarily involved in CoPs and NCC FGs
- Quadrant III Low Influence – Low Interest: They are mostly recipients of Communication and Dissemination actions.
- Quadrant IV Low Influence – High Interest: They could be involved in CoP on interest areas, Surely they are involved in NCC FGs

Table 2. A provisional overview of the different stakeholders and their engagement in the different NCC and CoP activities:

	National KICK-OFF	Focus group 1	Focus group 2	Focus group 3	Interviews farmers and advisors	Survey	Interviews policymakers	Multi-actor co-creation events (CoP kick-off etc.)	NoP level activities (workshops)
Scientific community and education	x		x	x				x	x
Farmers & advisors	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x
Cooperatives, producers' organisations	x		x	x				x	x
Input providers	x		x	x				x	x
Agri-food supply (processors to retail)	x							x	x
Society and consumers	x							x	x
Policymakers	x						x	x	x
Public bodies	x							(x)	x
Timing	May - June'23	May '23-Sept '23	Dec '23-August '24	Sept '24-June '25	Sept '23-Dec '24	Dec '23-March '24	June '23 - Oct '23	Sept - Dec '23	Whole project
Part of	WP4	WP4	WP4	WP4	WP2	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5
In function of	All NCC and CoP activities	T1.1	T1.3	T1.3	T2.2	T2.3	T3.1	T4.3	T5.4
Expected workload (days) (=preparation+reporting)	1.5 d	±3 d (inventory:1.5 d + prep.: 1 d + report: 0.5 d)						Depending on the type of event . In person: prep.2.5 d; report 0.5. On-line: prep.: 1.5 d + report: 0.5 d	
Deadline report	/	30/09/'23							

Funded by the European Union. Horizon Europe Grant Agreement Nr. 101084527. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

3. NCC Focus Groups

In SUPPORT 3 Focus groups will take place each of the selected crops will held as a part of the supporting activities to WP 1. They will follow the pace of the project and will be devoted to i) the definition of an inventory of current crop protection tools and practices for T1.1 (ii) design of the IPM strategies for each NCC by relying on the inventory provided in T1.1, the current IPM strategies will be described in 25 NCC reports (D4.2) (iii) design of future IPM scenarios by testing the IPM monitoring system from T1.2.

Focus groups allow, through discussion among participants, the deepening of specific topics. In a focus groups contents rise from interactions among participants. Therefore, in order to foster a climate as much as possible conducive to discussion and meaningful insights, FG must be carefully organized. In the following paragraph few tips and guidelines are provided on that.

3.1 Guidelines for effective Organization of Focus Groups

What is a focus group?

- ✓ Initial exploration, to define a goal (e.g. research question)
- ✓ Finding the best way to achieve a goal (e.g. research design)
- ✓ Implementation of a project (e.g. data collection)
- ✓ Assessment: understanding what happened & learning lessons (e.g. evaluate outcome)

Why focus groups?

Focus groups enable co-creation and collect qualitative data through group discussions. This research method can be used for different reasons: (1) exploration and discovery, (2) context and depth and (3) interpretation.

Researchers can use these guided group discussions to:

- learn about topics or groups of people that are poorly understood/they are not familiar with,

- gain insight into people’s behaviour, thoughts, and experiences,
- understand the essence of why certain things happened the way they did (interpret results, evaluate outcomes, and learn lessons).

In SUPPORT, the goal of the first focus group is to contribute to the making of the IPM inventory in T1.1, which on its turn will be the base for building the current IPM scenarios in T4.2.1 (focus group 2). The expertise from the focus group participants can be used to get feedback on the preparations, add missing information and extra IPM tools, discuss which tools are used most often and why. In addition, the focus group will be used to discuss possible barriers and levers during the decision making of choosing IPM strategies (feeds into WP2).

How to organise a focus group?

STEP 1: PLANNING

- ✓ Define the goal of the focus group: what do you want to achieve?
- ✓ Who should participate?
- ✓ Which questions will you ask?
- ✓ Take care of the logistics (location, timing, catering, agenda)

STEP 2: RECRUITING PARTICIPANTS

- Purposive sampling strategy (↔ random sampling strategy): Choose focus group participants according to the project’s goals to generate the most productive discussions during focus groups. Identify stakeholders with the right knowledge.
- Have a protocol for contacting potential participants (e.g. using an email template to ask for their participation).
- After the first contact, make sure to have follow-up contacts to ensure participants will attend the focus group.

STEP 3: MODERATING FOCUS GROUPS

- Good moderator = key.
- Moderator arrives 30 minutes beforehand to prepare the room.
- Facilitating focus groups: 1 or more facilitators?

- One or more facilitators?

The different roles of facilitators during a focus group are often combined:

- Moderation: guiding the focus group.
- Taking notes/recording the conversation.

Decide beforehand whether you will take notes or record the focus group!

- Monitoring: keep overview during the discussion, track time.
- Support: help with some practicalities during the focus group.
- Skills of the facilitator?

STEP 4: ANALYSING AND REPORTING

- ✓ Data = conversations.
- ✓ Analysis via transcripts, tapes, notes, memory.
- ✓ Using software for coding the data.
- ✓ Report your insights/key findings, not literal transcription!

4. Community of Practice

A community of Practice (CoP from now on), as it is commonly understood, is a *group of people who share a common concern, a set of problems, or an interest in a topic and who come together to fulfil both individual and group goals*. Such a definition is the result of the application of CoP methodology over time in a variety of social and economic context, that has contributed to shape it's definition, elaborated for the first time by Lave & Wegner in 1991 from being connected to learning as a meaning to foster identity and sense of belonging to communities that shares common practices (e.g.: workers in a factory), to that of a tool for knowledge sharing and co-creation of new contents. Despite changes in paradigm, the core concept beneath CoP theory has remained the same: i.e., the idea that knowledge is a property enacted by groups of people over time in shared practices, rather than something someone possess once and for good.

Yet another focus group?

CoP are not Focus Groups, although FGs could be used as a way to elicit participation in a CoP; therefore participation to one doesn't exclude participating to the other. While FG is a **research method** that brings together a small group of people to answer questions in a moderated setting, CoP is about a group of stakeholders who share a common concern or problem. CoPs tend to be local, hands-on and often, if not mainly, in-person, so retain the power of tacit knowledge in which individuals can intimately show what they do as well as describe it within a conducive environment and atmosphere.

CoP members have a **shared purpose** (*common concern*), over which \participants interests, competences and commitment converge. This shared domain creates common ground, inspires members to participate, guides their learning, and gives meaning to their actions.

In SUPPORT project such a common concern is stated in the proposal: "*To pave the way for the adoption of IPM tools and technologies*". Such a common concern will hopefully bound Project members to the stakeholders that will be involved in the Cops.

Being a **community**, its members pursue this interest through joint activities, discussions, problem-solving opportunities, information sharing and relationship building. The notion of a community creates the social fabric for enabling collective learning. The stronger the community is, the more fruitful will be interactions and willingness to share ideas.

In pursuing such objectives, CoPs members are not starting from scratch, as they are **actual practitioners** in this domain of interest, and therefore can build a shared repertoire of resources and ideas that they take back to their practice. While the domain provides the general area of interest for the community, the practice is the specific focus around which the community develops, shares and maintains its core of collective knowledge.

In **SUPPORT community of Practices (CoPs)** of the target crop systems will be set up to discuss the results, co-create the project outcomes and debate on the feasibility, implications and next steps to developing and implementing a harmonised EU approach for reducing use of plant protection products.

The total number of CoPs will be 9 and these will engage 135 actors in co-creation activities (15 per CoP).

A total number of 32 in person co-creation meetings of the CoPs will be held at local/national level.

4.1 Setting up of the CoP

The preparation of the CoPs will consider the following key principle :

- *Clear definition of goals, activities and lifecycle of the CoPs:* the goal of SUPPORT CoPs is co-developing strategies and policy recommendations that will contribute to an harmonised EU approach for reducing use of chemical plant protection products. In this view, the CoPs will represent a common space to share knowledge and practices, generating new knowledge and help participants changing practices.
- *Transdisciplinary of the composition:* The CoPs must consist of different typologies of actors from a variety of disciplines, such as farmers, advisors, researchers, academics and civil society representatives. This will allow including a plural-sided perspectives on the specific matter of common interest. CoPs will be composed by public and private, local and national actors to co-create strategies and policy. These actors will be identified based on the results of the stakeholder mapping conducted by T1.4.
- *Identification of a leader.* This will be up to the CoP that, since the first phase of the CoP will nominate a **Leader** that will act as moderator of the co-creation processes and as agent of cross-pollination among crop systems, both country and consortium-wise.

Facilitating successful workshops using the 8 P's

Source: *Communities of Practice in Higher Education on behalf of ODHE Network [Bultoc, D., Clarke, S., Devis-Rozental, C., Hubbard S., Roper, L., & Sinha, T. 2021]*

- *Conscious and well-prepared facilitation of the CoP:* it is fundamental to maintain energy and vitality across the CoP, in view to help its development over the lifecycle and without losing momentum, interest and/or contributions. If needed for the leaders, ad hoc training will be conducted by the WP4 core team through online workshops, facilitation guidelines and it will be provided in national languages.
- *Establish and share methods and tools for an effective CoP operationalization.* An effective approach to community facilitation involves creating a well-combined combination of face-to-face meetings, virtual meetings and a dialogue platform that, as a whole, provides a “predictable rhythm” of the CoPs lifetime. This makes the participants feeling to belong to the CoP’s space through creating the sense of community.

4.2 Fostering a shared vision: Appreciative Inquiry

Although the purpose of SUPPORT CoPs is set at project level, the way to pursue it, the connected challenges and barriers to overcome, as well as related opportunities, aims and desiderata, could vary from CoP to CoP. It is therefore necessary to foster a common understanding of the Cop objectives by adapting the main vision to local context.

A very common way to do that is by the **Appreciative Inquiry (AI) method**, which is also the paradigm adopted by SUPPORT.

AI is focused on opportunities, not on problems, It therefore moves from “problem solving” to the common search of the best way to achieve a goal. It is based on the assumption that a focus on problems and asking questions about how to solve them (the traditional approach for tackling societal issues), tends to keep attention on particular pre-determined path directions and goals so that stakeholders become stuck in a path-dependent mindset. In contrast, AI enables new theories and models of organising, planning for the future and improving society to be developed, which will often look very different from those derived from just trying to solve quite specific problems, which may, in fact, not be the key problems (Bushe 2013). Appreciative inquiry attempts to envision the future and formulate questions to foster positive relationships and build on the potentials of people, organisations or situations, in terms of their skills, capacities, resources and ideas.

AI develops over 5 phases (the 5 Ds)

- 1) Definition; What are the challenges facing the CoP?
- 2) Discovery: search and identify what already works in the field of interest (i.e.: Adoption of IPM practice)
- 3) Dream: it’s the first step of co-creation phase, where community members discuss what is needed to achieve high level results (ideally one – or many – steps further in respect to Discovery phase)
- 4) Design: For the dream to come true, what is needed?
- 5) Delivery a strategy: How will the Community achieve its objectives?

Figure 3: Appreciative Inquiry 5 Ds

Source: Authors' elaboration

An example applied to SUPPORT. AI applied to the adoption of IPMs strategy

AI phases	Connected issues	Question to Submit to the CoP
Definition of the Issue	Policies and strategies that could enhance reduction of pesticide use by a greater share of farmers	
Discovery	examples of success stories; what has worked in places where crops are grown in compliance with IPM rules?	What has worked? Who has been involved, What are the results on the field?
Dream	Given the state of the art, what might be? How we can convince farmers toward sustainable pest management	What is desirable to go further in IPM adoption?
Design	Which steps are necessary to bring farmers to full adoption of IPM?	Identify barriers, enabling environment, drivers to adoption...
Delivery	Arrange issues and ways to address them in coherent strategies	tools and assets to achieve desired goals

A shared vision for SUPPORT project

SUPPORT aims at paving the road for the reaching of the Farm to fork objectives by contributing to 1) identify the barriers and the drivers to transition 2) by translating them in meaningful insights for policymaking ad 3) contributing to the holistic monitoring of IPM use impacts

Once the vision is set, there's the need of a roadmap to pursue it. This is somehow traced by the project activities and their timing, although CoP management it's entirely up to national partners.

According to project agreement , there must be at least one in person CoP meeting per year, but the CoP could be summoned every time it is deemed necessary by mean on on-line tools, CoP will support each phase of the project activities, from which they will receive inputs for co creation and discussion, with specific sessions on policy making.

CoP1 - First CoP meeting must be done by the end of 2023. it will deal with the discussion of barriers and drivers to the adoption of IPM practices and to the first round of discussions on how to build policies to curb the firsts and foster the seconds (T1.1. & T3.2)

CoP2 -Second in person CoP meeting must be held from M12 to M24 and will support the development of the holistic monitoring system (T.1.2)

CoP3 -The third meeting (M24 – M36) will deal with the fine tuning of the monitoring system and testing its application (T 1.3)

CoP4 - Fourth CoP will use the inputs coming from the projects (application of the monitoring system, results of the quali—quantitative interviews, identification of future strategies for IPM uptake) in order to develop a feasible strategy toward greater sustainability in pest management, integrating insights form project activities into policy recommendations

Among these meeting further co-creation activities are envisaged, specifically aimed at cross-fertilization: 1 cross fertilization infra – CoP online meeting per year **CFM** (online) and specific exchange workshops (**EW**) among CoP leaders during project annual meetings. Two further meeting, during the project, will be devoted at connecting CoPs with their international stakeholders (**IM**)

Figure 4: CoPs Timeline in SUPPORT

Source: Authors' elaboration

4.3 Manage discussion in heterogeneous groups: the double diamond approach

Group discussion could be messy: usually people tend to jump to conclusions without taking the time to actually deepen the issues or the problem².

The Double Diamond- techniques is a moderation technique that help avoiding unfruitful discussions.

Following the Double Diamond technique you first focus on a proper understanding of an issue. Once there is agreement on a clear understanding of what is at stake, the second part of the discussion focusses on possible solutions or on what it takes to move forward.

In each section of the discussion, you first let the discussion diverge until the 'crunch zone': a stage in which different views and opinions might compete with each other. Then you converge towards a common understanding of the problem (first diamond) or solution or step forwards to overcome a challenge (second diamond).

Sometimes in the second diamond new insight appears for which it is necessary to go back to the first one. Then it is important to clearly mark this and get agreement of the group for doing so.

Problem Diamond

Explore: In this phase the problem/issue at stake is explored in all its facets. It's a **divergent phase**, because everyone could tell it's opinion and contribute to the discussion,

What is the state of the art of the issue that we are exploring?

Possible tools. Top down presentation of the state of the art to foster open discussion; Interviews to relevant stakeholders; Mind maps. Example: Which kind of policies is lacking for the effective uptake of IPM? Anyone could say his opinion, someone could write it on a sticky note and attach it on a board divided in topics (e.g.: financing, environmental legislation,

Concentrate: The concentrate step aims at getting to a shared understanding of the problem. it is the convergent part of the problem space as it allows ideas to be narrowed into a clear definition of the problem. Issues emerged in the exploration phase could be here arranged in priorities. Following the example above, the sticky notes could be gathered according to overarching themes (e.g.. financing, legislation...); open discussion could contribute to further specify the different facets of the issues at stake.

Solution Diamond

The solution diamond is where a leap forward from what has been discussed in the previous phase is made. Here new ideas are developed, there room for exploration. For instance, sticking to the example of the policies. How to make a lacking policy work (to whom it

² Please note that we are shifting the focus of the tool, in respect to Appreciative Inquiry: AI is a methodology used to facilitate positive change at CoP level; DD Technique is a design thinking approach used in problem-solving and innovation processes.. While AI is commonly applied in organizational settings, DD is primarily used in the field of innovation. Therefore, AI aims at fostering a common sense of "working toward the same goal" in CoPs, DD supports the development of innovative solutions to a challenge.

could be addressed, How should be implemented/enforced)? This is a divergent phase, because everyone is entitled to express his thoughts.

Lastly, discussion must be led to producing feasible solutions. Here agreement is sought upon what has been explored in the last divergent phase. For instance by voting, by gathering similar insights in overarching topics...and so on

Figure 5 : The Double Diamond Technique

Source: H2020 I2Connect tools for Interactive Innovation

4.4 What is co-creation?

Co-creation processes must be activated every time there is a shared ambition (agreement on problem and target) but the solution and the way to find such a solution cannot be decided beforehand. Unlike top-down knowledge transfer and the desired outcome is not fixed and unlike other form of knowledge exchange, outcomes are not a results of a negotiation. Co creation processes answer the question: "What can we make possible if we would pool our resources?" Focus is therefore on ambitions actors share, rather than on possible outcomes. Co-creation can lead to results that are better than you could have imagined beforehand.

Figure 6: Methods for communication

Source: H2020 I2Connect tools for Interactive Innovation

Co-creation is based on two complementary processes: cooperation and collaboration, they of course could happen separately but in a co-creation path they must integrate through coordination.

Cooperation: everyone brings it's own contribution, according to his expertise

Collaboration: These pieces of knowledge are brought together in order to build something new

Figure 7: Cooperation – Collaboration - Coordination

Source: Authors' elaboration

Each co-creation process needs facilitation: which is the art of for creating space for collaboration for people who's already willing to cooperate.

Facilitators make it easy for people in the group to participate and to give their contributions. They do whatever is needed for allowing participants to concentrate of the contents of their joint endeavour. They act like the travel agency that ensures that their clients can enjoy without any worries. Facilitators allows the functioning of the group, He/she:

1. Regulates the interventions (keeps tracks of the requests to speak, hands raised, politely ask whoever lingers in speaking to be short),
2. Collects main finding and report them to the groups (summarizes main topics of the discussion in order to open a new one)
3. Valorises and sums up differences
4. Fosters an easy and conducive environment for discussion (by preparing the (virtual) room for the meeting and checking that everything works, by refraining from any kind of judgement, avoiding downtimes etc..).

According to Rogers (1957) the facilitator must have three facilitating characteristics (table 3), that , besides guaranteeing the functioning of the group, should contribute in fostering a climate that is perceived by everyone as safe space to express their thoughts.

Table 3: characteristics of a good facilitator according to Rogers

Characteristic	Explanation	Example of correct behaviour
Empaty	ability to listen authentically to the interlocutor, with the honest intention of understanding his point of view and ideas	DO not interrupt people unless it is necessary for the sake of discussions. Do not correct someone statement!
Unconditional acceptance	acceptance of every experiences, refraining from any form of interpretation and/or judgement.	Facilitators is not allowed to express judgments on others's opinions!
Congruence	keeping in mind what facilitator's function and role are; avoiding any attempt of manipulation. There must be perfect match between what you say and How you behave!	Do not brag about your competences FGS could be boring: don't show impatience . Rather admit you are tired and ask for a break

4.5 Methodologies for the conduction of in-person meetings

Along the SUPPORT CoPs' lifecycles variety of engagement methods and tools will be applied to ensure creating an enabling environment for the different activities showed in table.

Table 4: Activities in CoP

Activity of the CoP	Purpose
(1) Building relationships within the CoP	Develop relationships of trust, mutual respect, reciprocity, and commitment necessary for strong communities
(2) Learn and co-develop the practice	Learn and develop a shared practice, based on an existing body of knowledge
(3) Take collective action as a community	Take purposeful action to carry out tasks and projects
(4) Co-create new knowledge for practice for reducing use of plant protection products	Generate and discover new knowledge

Open space technology ([A Brief User's Guide to Open Space Technology by Harrison Owen](#))

What, for which purposes and with which benefits

OST will be used by the CoPs of SUPPORT for co-creation of innovative solutions.

This methodology helps finding innovative solutions in an uncertain and/complex environment by leveraging collective intelligence and people's ability to self-organise. Participants must care about the theme/objective and be committed to active learning and knowledge, opinions and experiences sharing. The methodology allows organizing workshop of a large number (e.g. 500 pp) participants. The minimum number of participant is 20. The OST is based on a single rule and four principles:

The two-foot law - Whenever happens, each participant must recognize that she/he's not able to learn/contribute anymore to the meeting and simply she/he takes the responsibility to use own two feet to move somewhere else to contribute more effectively.

This implies that, some participants will act as bumblebees, by flying from group to group through cross-pollinating the discussions; others will act as Butterflies that just sit around and benefitting from the discussions around them.

The principles are:

1. People who come to the group are the right ones. It does not matter who or how many and most of all, it does not matter who is missing. What it is fundamental is high interest, passion and commitment.
2. What happens is the only thing that can happen.
3. When it starts, it starts.
4. When it ends, it ends.

How to apply the method during CoPs meetings

The OST has an open format since its development is under the responsibility of participants. It aims at stimulating creativity about a certain theme/objective in view to find the solution. The overall framework for an OST event must ensure creating the enabling environment for knowledge sharing, collective learning and co-creation. OST events lasting up to one day are based on four elements: Opening, Agenda Setting, Open Space, and Conclusion. Additional elements for event that last up to two days are Morning Announcements, Evening News, and probably a Celebration (table below).

<p>1. <i>Opening</i>— The aim is socializing, getting familiar one to each other. Informal openings, like aperitives or dinners, are well suited to build trust among participants. Here a “knowing each other” exercise is well suited to introduce participants one to each other.</p>	<p>2. <i>Agenda setting</i>— Normally an Open Space event has no pre-defined agenda as this is defined by the participants during a kick-off meeting or the very beginning of the event. This is the time for the group to figure out what it wants to do. In this moment what it is of overarching importance is defining the theme which is of common interest and it must have the capacity to be appealing and inspire participation “<i>by being specific enough to indicate the direction, while possessing sufficient openness to allow for the imagination of the group to take over</i>”. Do not set the schedule as there should be not interruptions to the dialogue. When it ends it ends. In SUPPORT OST, the theme will specifically define for each event coherently with the phase of CoP development and activities to carry out.</p>
<p>3. <i>Open space</i>— This is the moment for the introduction of the event, by providing</p>	<p>4. <i>Closing</i> — The closing session is open but directed to define concluding comments</p>

<p>the overview of the OST methodology and workflow of the session, explaining the rule and principles, the theme and expected outcomes. Then you literally open the space to participants and their self-organization in sessions/groups. Comfortable space and large enough for breakouts are a must. Participants are organized in circle or semicircle. No tables, no obstacles to movements of participants. Chairs must be removable. The facilitator will be since now one step behind the groups. The floor is for the participants.</p>	<p>by participates (what I bring home, what it meant by me), final reporting, announcing commitments, next steps, propositions to do. Space must be open without obstacles between the facilitator and the participants. Better for the facilitator to start anywhere and go around the circle allowing each participant, on voluntary basis, to speak.</p>
<p><i>Evening news</i> — This is a time for story-telling, reflection and some fun. The story-telling exercise is appropriate to fit the purpose of this session.</p>	<p><i>Celebration</i>— This is a time devoted to self-celebration for the work done, undertakings, decisions taken for further actions and the innovative solutions that have been co-created. It’s nothing serious but all about fun. A nice exercise is the COCONUT stretching where the facilitator shows the group how to spell out C-O-C-O-N-U-T by using full movements of the arms and the body. All participants then try this together.</p>
<p><i>Announcements</i>— These will be just wrap-up sessions aimed at catching up on what it is going on and how. Just facts telling the story of what the group is doing over the OST.</p>	<p><i>Final reporting</i>— This session risks to be non-productive and boring and very often little time is allocated to groups reporting. So, organize things to end the event with final reports to bring home by the participants. Organizing on-site reporting/noting through a computer within each group is very appropriate to allow printing out the reports and hanging them on the walls so to provide on-going record of the discussions in sessions. This will help also reporting during the closing session (4). Additionally, cartoon designers/graphic recorders can be appointed to follow the sessions and draw the paths of the respective discussions.</p>

Material

A checklist for OST planning can be found [here](#). It is a good practice to provide a template for reporting.

Rooms should be large to allow positioning participants in circles and break-outs and also to divide participants by groups.

Flipcharts, post-it, ink markers and tapes are needed.

Food and beverage must be available all the time so people can eat when they want to.

European awareness scenario

What, for which purposes and with which benefits

The EAS will be used by the CoPs of SUPPORT for co-creation of innovative solutions that take into adequate consideration different point of views of relevant actors and to ensure smooth applications on fields.

An Awareness Scenario Workshop is a participatory method that combines the creation of space for deliberative discussion (workshop approach) within a multistakeholder environment around a topic/matter and the scenario building around actual opportunities for change and potential future issues that could emerge from decisions (scenario building

approach). In this view, it is particularly adequate to create common understanding, awareness, encouraging collective decision and ownership, thus prompt follow-up up, about innovative solutions.

EAS is particularly adequate to SUPPORT CoPs as it leads the participants involved in defining the correlation between the long-term expectations on change and the priority actions to run in the short/medium term in view to achieve it. In fact, EAS promotes among participants the sense of responsibility for the role they can act in promoting the expected change, so to be actors of the desired change.

How to apply the method during CoPs meetings

Differently from the OST, the EASW is rigorously structured along two or three days of workshop and around two fields of action scenario visioning and idea development. The workshop is to be developed following the a stepwise approach:

1. Visioning: participants are divided in groups in relation of the different typologies of actors: farmers, advisors, researchers, policy makers. The facilitator introduces the topic and invites participants to develop visions for addressing the topical matter of common interest like they were in the future. For each group the facilitator must use a mix of techniques including mediation, animation and discussion facilitation.
2. Scenario building: At the end of the parallel sessions, the different visions will be presented and voted in plenary (for example by using ranking method, three star voting method) to find the one most suitable/likely for all the all the participants. This vision must be very detailed in defining the actions (what) to be taken and the organization of roles (who) to play by the different groups. Ones the common vision is achieved and well-defined, this will be at the basis for the next phase.
3. Idea development. Participants are divided in groups by themes that are key for the common vision, so that the composition reflects the plurality of interests and competences of them. The facilitator introduces the session by explaining the common vision and asking for up to 5 ideas for its operationalization. The idea development includes listing actions to take and responsibilities by each type of participant. The facilitator will use techniques like focus group, the [Disney method](#), [SCAMPER method](#) and [idea challenge](#).
4. Action planning: ideas are discussed and voted for selection. the most voted ideas will be at the basis of the action plan that will be defined during a plenary session. Techniques like metaplan and others will be used to facilitates this phase.

The EASW will be organised around two central questions: (1) WHO is responsible for make the desired change; (2) HOW the change can be make real; which is the most feasible scenario?

Material

Other material is due to the facilitation techniques that are put in use during the different phases of the workshop.

Rooms should be large to allow positioning participants in circles and break-outs and also to divide participants by groups.

³ The EC has the license for the use of this methodology and provides a guide at <http://www.cordis.lu/easw>

Food and beverage are better to be available all the time by avoiding stop the work sessions.

Bibliographic Material

Already inserted in the text.

Hackathon

What, for which purposes and with which benefits

A "hackathon" provides a space and a time for participants to make progress on or solve some particular real-life problems (challenges), in a friendly and fairly competition between projects.

It assumes that some participants bring project ideas (hatchers) to join and others are just interested to learn and gather knowledge about the topical matter. It will help benefitting from the competition between ideas and team working to upgrade innovative solutions.

It includes different types of events (marathon) as in whole it addresses hacking innovative, strengthening relations among participants and attracting/training newcomers.

How to apply the method during CoPs meetings

In SUPPORT both the two formats of hackathon will be applied according to the different stages of the CoPs development: (1) Fast Rabbit: it last up to 2/3 days and it is designed to promote the hatching of quickly innovative solutions; (2) Wise Turtle: it normally lasts up to one month and it addresses more complex issues during a continue developing of the hackathon.

Organizing a hackathon requires quite much preliminary efforts mainly to apply for planning, that includes defining a hackathon team of organizers (compositions should reflect the plurality of participants), participants who will bring ideas, format and needed resources, definition of challenges to tackle and target groups communication, and communication to the participants.

The hackathon is then developed as in the following steps:

Step 1: Opening and pitch session of the event, including the presentation of the rules of the game and the Pitch session during with the Hatchers introduce Ideas for innovative solutions (1 min max) with the view to engage participants.

Step 2: Teams constitution. Participants constitute teams around the competing ideas.

Step 3: Start of activities. Teams develop the innovative idea by discussion. No leaders. Everyone can leave the team whenever wanted.

Step 4: Delivery of results and Presentation Pitch (5 min each) of the innovative solutions that each team has developed.

Step 5: Selection of winners and Prize Award.

Step 6: wrap-up and Follow up. The wrap-up session gives everyone a chance to hear what everyone else worked on during the day. For a small group, ask volunteers to report what they accomplished or what they learned (especially for workshop participants). Give folks rounds of applause.

Material

Open space (outdoor is the best), colourful and friendly environment. The location must be well organized for individual laptops, projectors and microphones, little tables, free Wi-Fi and charging stations.

Everything must be recorded for the public, through photos, videos, in particular shooting also small interview to participants.

Facilitation material includes posters, banners, post-its and other typical facilitation material.

Food and beverage must be available during the sessions.

Bibliographic Material

<https://hackathon.guide>

<https://guide.mlh.io/>

<https://www.mediawiki.org/wiki/Hackathons/Timeline>

4.6 Co-creation and interaction through asynchronous tools

One of the objectives to be pursued in order to ensure the smooth functioning of CoPs is to keep the participation of the different actors alive and dynamic throughout its life cycle and to create a sense of community among them, so that participants can develop sound relationships and everyone can express him/herself without any fear of sharing his/her own experience and discuss/analyse that of others, contributing to the growth of the group's knowledge.

This objective cannot be pursued only through in-person workshops and kick-offs due to the unavailability of time on the part of the members and financial resources within the project. Therefore, face-to-face meetings must be held alongside virtual ones using specific platforms (Project's Teams, Zoom, Google Meet, etc.), social networks (Telegram, WhatsApp, etc.) and interactive tools (Mentimeter, Mural, etc.), each with its own peculiarities. This "Place" (Bultoc et al. 2023), which will become a virtual room that can be easily accessed by people territorially located in places far apart the one from each other.

On the other hand, mixing face-to-face meetings and virtual ones allow greater amount of exchanges in CoPs. With the former, in fact, members "*put themselves out there for it*", and show their interest in participating by having to physically move from a place to another. Above all, they have the opportunity to build informal relationships, thanks also to the time spent together in socializing activities (icebreakers, coffee breaks, meals). At this end, face to face meetings foster sociability. The camaraderie and fellowship that should be created in that way among CoP members, will help in fostering discussion in subsequent face-to-face meetings.

Virtual meetings, on the other hand, can ensure continuous communication through the activation of different types of tools that allow for synchronous and asynchronous discussions (through, for instance, online forums/chats, recordings of meetings that could not be attended, etc.). The latter are very important but complementary to synchronous discussions. Depending on the situation or the need that arises, asynchronous discussions allow for an update on the state of the art even for very busy people who may find it difficult to grant their presence at CoP meetings. The availability of a longer period of time to reflect and formulate their own thoughts or judgements on specific issues they are

called upon to respond to, as well as the possibility of making proposals of various kinds themselves when they see the need avoids the loss of participants along the process.

Virtual meetings, moreover, ease the use of supplementary materials (video, photos, supporting software) as a tool for fostering sharing and gathering of opinions.

It is therefore a matter of understanding what are the elements that characterise a CoP and how it is possible to ensure their presence or reproduce them in virtual CoPs.

The vitality and dynamism of a CoP as well as of any other organisation of individuals depend on the development of social capital, which is defined by Cohen and Prusak (2001) as a set of connections based on trust, mutual understanding, shared values and behaviours that bind the members of a community allowing the development of co-operative actions.

The first element in building strong relationships within a CoP, therefore, is the trust placed by each member in the others, trust that leads them to share their knowledge and experiences and to accept any advice and suggestion. Trust, however, is built over time and it is precisely the possibility of combining face-to-face meetings with virtual ones that allows its growing and strengthening.

The development of connections depends on the characteristics of the people who are part of the CoP and who make it successful, characteristics that lead them to be identified as connectors, experts and sellers.

Connectors are people who can create friendships and acquaintances very easily, thanks to a good dose of curiosity, self-esteem, sociability and energy. Experts create relationships by gathering and sharing information while salespeople convince undecided people to make a decision by inducing them to accept change or novelty as an opportunity for growth. The combined action of these three types of people makes the CoP effective, regardless of where it meets, physical or virtual, growing and strengthening.

Finally, the knowledge conveyed within the CoP can be explicit, easily expressible, codifiable and transferable, or tacit, also referred to as "tricks of the trade", which derives from the experience and insight of the individual, and therefore difficult to define and communicate, and delineates the very identity of a CoP as the "real holder" of a heritage of tacit knowledge (Coppola, 2008). The latter should become explicit through a process of socialisation, becoming the object of comparison and sharing within the CoP, through observation, imitation, practice and validation by other individuals, and of eventual transfer outside the same. Clearly, the different online tools that can be activated to ensure the smooth functioning of the CoP guarantee the coordinated management of both types of knowledge, in some respects even more effectively than face-to-face meetings, as they per se combine the tacit and explicit knowledge, especially when they permit dialogue (Castaneda & Toulson, 2021).

The management of COP also in an online mode requires the presence of certain elements such as (Coppola, 2008):

The activation of a platform for remote collaboration (e.g. Teams) with a section dedicated to the CoP members' biographies with photos, CVs and personal interests, if any, which help to improve the level of socialisation, hampered by physical distance, especially when people do not know each other;

The definition of a CoP graphic design, with its logo, general layout of the online environment, specific character of texts so as to make the community recognisable and identifiable;

Activation of services to allow for synchronous and asynchronous discussion, sharing of documents, videos, audio, images, etc.;

The activation of specific areas for the uploading and management of databases that can be consulted and implemented by all members (e.g. inventory of IPM practices)

The possibility of activating areas for sub-working groups.

Alongside such a platform, it would be useful to activate specific chats on social networks to foster relational aspects and the possibility of communicating whenever it is deemed important.

To this end, the following activities of a CoP need to be designed:

Analysis and definition of the context in which the community is localized.

Are on line tools feasible to each participants (quality of connection could change according to place, older people could not be used to such tools)? Are there alternative solutions?

Planning of a strategy that defines its aims and lines of development (see par. 4.2)

Planning of the communicational environment in which its participants interact.

Provide a tool for constant interaction between CoP leaders and participants (A blog, A forum, a mailing list)

Planning any the operational activity in time

Communicate upcoming meeting promptly, communicate the topic and the envisaged type and quality of the involvement that will be required, also by forwarding any useful material beforehand

Monitoring and evaluation of the activity and its possible development (see par 4.8).

On-line CoPs do not exclude facilitation. Indeed, the functions of the facilitator remain more or less the same: he/she fosters interaction among participants, managing information and suggesting new ideas, organising events (seminars, workshops, focus groups, etc.).

Nevertheless, there are relevant differences due to the relative ease with which exchanges take place during online discussions, during which participants have less difficulty expressing their opinions, even if they are at odds with (or even offensive to) other participants. Conversely, participants may be tempted to exclude themselves from the discussion more easily, protected by the 'technological barrier'. Therefore, the facilitator is asked to adopt an attitude of '**tough love**' (Davis & Denning, 2001).

Throughout a "tough love" attitude, facilitators succeed in nourish CoPs social capital, even if they are held online. In order to achieve that, he must be able in reckoning participants needs and feeling (e.g.: *this is an harsh thought, could you motivate it so that everybody could understand your point of view?*), he must help everyone in going beyond the comfort zone (e.g.: *I know you are and advisor with a longstanding experience on that, could you please share your opinion?*) and support group creativity (e.g.: *thank you for your contribution: it a very interesting point of view*). The facilitator is supported by a staff that also presides over the setting up of the virtual environment, the retrieval, organisation and management of information of various kinds through the various IT tools adopted and social networks activated. Then there are the external actors who participate as researchers, consultants, experts, entrepreneurs, etc. However, this structure must be flexible in the sense that it must adapt to the changing needs of the CoP according to the

stage of the life cycle it is in (incubation, development, maturation, consolidation, transformation).

Table 5: Pros and Cons of on-line co-creation activities

Opportunities	Treats
They are time saving and avoid travel, so that they do not cause oo much inconvenience in a working day	Sometimes participants could feel overwhelmed by the load of information and actions they must undertake in order to follow the meeting agenda
They foster collaboration instead of competition	The time required to complete a task (e.g. answering a questionnaire) can be longer, compared to the same task carried out in presence
Asynchrnuos modalities allow more time for critical reflections and that is conducive to new insights	Learning new tools, especially when it comes to informatics could be hard
The access to online resources and tools is immediate	It is easy to misunderstand the assigned task, especially in the presence of poor information
There's always a direct access to facilitatoors and moderators	Conversation could become scattered, although participants could pretend an immediate answer
They are very inexpensive (free), moreover they reduce time and money for travel	More specific tools are costly (e.g.: subscription, development of <i>ad hoc</i> modules)

4.7 Lifecycle of the CoPs

CoPs will be accompanied through the respective lifecycles along the following phases:

Inquire: Through a process of exploration and inquiry, identify the audience, purpose, goals, and vision for the community.

Design: Define the activities, technologies, group processes, and roles that will support the community's goals.

Prototype: Pilot the community with a select group of key stakeholders to gain commitment, test assumptions, refine the strategy, and establish a success story.

Launch: Roll out the community to a broader audience over a period of time in ways that engage newcomers and deliver immediate benefits.

Grow: Engage members in collaborative learning and knowledge sharing activities, group projects, and networking events that meet individual, group, and organizational goals while creating an increasing cycle of participation and contribution.

Sustain: Cultivate and assess the knowledge and "products" created by the community to inform new strategies, goals, activities, roles, technologies, and business models for the future."

4.8 A tool for policy design: relational SWOT

Relational SWOT belongs to participatory methods and implies the active involvement of potential beneficiaries/stakeholders in the different phases of policy design, right from its conception.

In addition to the fact that the method itself does not present robustness characteristics, the classical SWOT shows a rather evident weakness, namely the fact that the four groups of elements that compose it (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats) are not related and there is no way of understanding whether, all together, they produce a favorable or unfavorable framework for the implementation of a policies/programmes, nor which actions can be taken to improve them. The main difficulty inherent in the SWOT analysis consists precisely in the correct cross-reading of the results.

Despite the critical issues highlighted, the SWOT is functional, if adequately structured, to provide a synthetic (but exhaustive) representation of the main characteristics of a topic helping to facilitate the identification of possible development trajectories (Zanon and Martignano, 2007). In complex contexts, such as that of CAP, it can help identify the most appropriate strategy and priority actions to improve the competitiveness and sustainability of the regional agricultural, agri-food and forestry sector. In this sense, the SWOT can be taken as part of a knowledge process to support decisions.

In order to overcome the limits mentioned above, it is possible to carry out a **relational SWOT** based on the pairwise comparison between the "n" elements identified in the SWOT, regardless of the category to which they belong.

The exercise consists of a series of steps which, especially in the initial phase, should envisage the active contribution of actors for the identification of the development drivers, as well as the impeding factors and the needs to be satisfied. In a nutshell, the elements of the model for each phase are exemplified below.

- **PHASE 1** : identification of the characteristics (strengths and weaknesses) and of the factors of the external context (opportunities and threats) of the topic to be analysed (e.g.: reduce by 50% the use and risk of chemical pesticides by 2030), starting from the existing context
- **PHASE 2** : aggregation of similar elements, in order to obtain a smaller number of elements for each reference framework (strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats)
- **PHASE 3** : the elements chosen in the two previous phases are reported both in the horizontal and in the vertical header of a double entry matrix (table X). The pairwise comparisons are then carried out by comparing each row element with each column element (one at a time) and a score is assigned.
 - -2, if the row element is strongly hindered or cancelled by the column one,
 - -1, if the row element is hindered by the column one (however it develops its own effects);
 - 0, when the elements considered do not influence each other (mutual independence between the two elements compared),
 - +1, if the row element is increased by the column element (the effects of the first are amplified by the second),
 - +2, if the row element is strongly incremented by the column element.

Figure 8: Matrix for Relational SWOT

		1).....	2).....	3).....	1).....	2).....	3).....	1).....	2).....	3).....	1).....	2).....	3).....	
		S				W			O			T		
S	1).....	■												
	2).....		■											
	3).....			■										
W	1).....				■									
	2).....					■								
	3).....						■							
O	1).....							■						
	2).....								■					
	3).....									■				
T	1).....										■			
	2).....											■		
	3).....												■	
		Sum per column (absolute values)												

Source: Authors' elaboration

During this phase participants reflect on how row elements are influenced by column elements. A value is then assigned to the first as dependent variables and to the second as independent variables. Each point of the SWOT will therefore be both an influenced element and an influencing element. During the process it is possible to run into the so-called problem of the counter-intuitive element: if an element of weakness or threat is strengthened in its negative potential by a factor, more or less strongly, it means that the latter contributes to increasing the negativity of the relationship, therefore the score in these cases becomes positive. There could also be situations of disagreement in the attribution of values: in the event that unanimity is not reached, the will of the majority will be reported, taking note of the difficulty/disagreement. It could be useful to reflect on these elements in a subsequent phase of refinement of the regional needs/strategy.

- **PHASE 4** : this phase is devoted to the actual evaluation, considering the relevance of the factors and their reciprocal influence.

From an operational point of view, the matrices are processed considering the row and column totals according to a double reading key. Since the row vectors express the weight of the individual elements regardless of the category they belong to (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats) in relation to all the others, the higher total (row) values provide indications on which elements are able to influence others more. Furthermore, through the latter it is possible to evaluate whether it is the elements with a positive value (strength, opportunity) that are more important, or those with negative connotations (weakness, threats). The column vectors indicate the force and direction that the individual elements exert on the others. In this case, the sums are calculated on the absolute values. The column totals provide a trace of the elements which appear to have the greatest influence on the others and which, therefore, are considered the *drivers* or *moderators* of the process: through these latter it may possibly be possible to act to improve the strategy (for more information).

4.9 Monitoring and evaluation of the multistakeholder approach

According to OECD (2009), monitoring refers to a continuing function that uses systematic collection of data on specified indicators to provide management and the main stakeholders of an ongoing [...] intervention with indications of the extent of progress and achievement of objectives and progress in the use of allocated funds" (OECD, 2009[39]). Therefore, it aims to ensure that the initiative is on track and that it is achieving the intended results, enabling initiatives to be modified and adapted if necessary.

Evaluation refers to "the systematic and objective assessment of an ongoing or completed project, programme or policy, its design, implementation and results. The aim is to determine the relevance and fulfilment of objectives, [...] efficiency, effectiveness, impact and sustainability".

Monitoring and evaluation are therefore different but complementary practices, that allow the individual or group conducting the assessment to understand how they are performing and progressing to enable improvement (Holzer et al., 2018). Evaluation implies providing a judgement on an observed phenomenon, while monitoring provides the tools for getting to an effective evaluation. Since most of natural and socio economic phenomena are complex and often hard to be described, assessment is made through indicators, which essentially are summary measure, usually expressed in quantitative form, coinciding with a variable or composed of several variables, capable of summarise the trend of the phenomenon to which they are referred to (for instance the GDP per capita is and indicator of the wealth of a Country).

SUPPORT multi -actor evaluation framework will be used to check where the multiactor approach is going, so to provide evidence for the need of correcting the route, if any. In order to achieve such a result it will make use of appropriate indicators. Indicators could refer to the immediate outputs of the participatory processes, i.e. those that deal with their operationalization (e.g.: Number of stakeholder involved per event, number of co-creation initiatives per type etc.)) and to those that concern its effects on participation (outcome). Indicators of impacts, instead, deal with the long term effects of participation, and therefore concern permanent the influence of the community on individual learning, organizational performance, innovation, and knowledge transfer. The focus here is on positive outcomes, such as improved practices, enhanced decision-making, or increased efficiency. While outputs are easily measurable, outcomes and impacts are hard to quantify, as they deal with the qualitative aspects of actors participation. Nevertheless, they will be integrated with overall performance monitoring and evaluation that ultimately feeds back into the strategy for stakeholders engagement.

Participatory approaches must be evaluated against criteria that are able to grasp the effectiveness of the activated processes by considering factors like engagement levels, knowledge creation and sharing, member satisfaction, collaboration, and the practical application of knowledge; they therefore concern outcomes that are intangible in nature that is why evaluation is usually carried out by mean of interviews to participants (Holzer et al., 2018) for instance, on the perceived degree of involvement of targeted stakeholder community, the effectiveness of participation tools, the actual influence on project outcomes and so on.

Output indicators

Output indicators concern the process itself; they provide a tangible and easy measure of the effectiveness of the action undertaken. They do not describe the reasons why a project is started, but rather describe the goodness of the means to an end.

Table 6: Output indicators for SUPPORT multi-actor approach

Criteria	Indicator	Application	Frequency
Involvement	Number of participant per event (target = 10/15)	FG, CoP, NoP	At each event
	Involvement rate (people attending/people contacted)	FG, CoP, NoP	At each event
Diversity of participants/organisations	Male /female	FG, CoP, NoP	At each event
	Participant per type	FG, CoP, NoP	At each event
	Age*	FG, CoP, NoP	At each event
recruitment/retention of (new) members	Substitution rate (new members /total participants)	CoP, NoP	At each event
Organization	Frequency of the CoPs events (baseline 1 in presence event /year)	CoP	Year
	CoP Events per type		Year
Transparency	Type of feedbacks provided (meeting minutes, registration...)	FG, CoP, NoP	Year

- Young farmer according to EU definition

Outcomes

Outcomes refer to short-term and long-term changes resulting from actors involvement and therefore deal with the immediate results of co-creation. Since these results are intangible can be detected and measured only by qualitative means (When et al., 2021), the most common of which is the close -ended questionnaire, to be submitted to participant at the end of an event or on a regular basis (once every six months, once per year...) depending on the objective of the assessment (the single meeting or the overall involvement strategy).

As general role participants are asked to state the degree of agreement on items concerning their actual involvement in the co-creation procedure. The agreement is expressed in a likert scale where 1 in total disagreement and 4 is total agreement (the higher the happier)

Example: State the level of agreement on this statement: During the workshop, I always felt free to state my opinions

1	Don't agree at all
2	I Somewhat don't agree

3	I Somewhat agree
4	Completely agree

If your answer is ≤ 2 , could you please provide a little explanation?

Blackstock et al, (2007) have identified several criteria for evaluation of participatory approaches that exemplify the elements for evaluating the effectiveness of stakeholder involvement.

Table 7. Evaluative criteria for participatory research (modified form Blackstock et al, 2007)

Criteria	Description	Application
Access to resources	Referring to provision of support to allow participants to engage and meet expectations for their roles	
	<i>The objective and the focus of the meeting was clear</i>	<i>FG; CoP; NoP</i>
	<i>Beforehand the meeting I had all the information I needed for an aware participation</i>	
Accountability	Referring to whether the representative's core constituencies are satisfied, including expectations	
	<i>The contents developed in the meeting was relevant and consistent to my needs and interests.</i>	<i>CoP; NoP</i>
	<i>I had the opportunity to state my opinion freely (enough space for discussion, adequacy of technical means)</i>	<i>FG; CoP; NoP</i>
Capacity to participate	Referring to the individual's ability to value different points of view and willingness to learn as well as their competence	
	<i>I felt comfortable in sharing my viewpoint.</i>	<i>FG; CoP; NoP</i>
Champion/leadership	Referring to the both internal leadership and champions but also the role of the critical outsider	
	<i>The facilitator was active in ensuring a good flow of the discussion.</i>	<i>FG; CoP; NoP</i>
	<i>I think that there was overrepresentation of opinions, interests.</i>	<i>FG; CoP; NoP</i>
	<i>I feel involved in any decision on the Community of Practice</i>	<i>CoP; NoP</i>
Quality of information	Referring to the adequacy, quality and quantity of information provided	
	<i>The results of the meeting are clear and consistent</i>	<i>CoP; NoP</i>
Relationships	Referring to issues of social capital through new and existing social networks developed during the process/project e.g. trust, reciprocity and collaboration	
	<i>Participants have worked effectively at the tasks that have been assigned to the group</i>	<i>CoP; NoP</i>
	<i>The outputs of the meeting result from collaboration among participants</i>	<i>CoP; NoP</i>
	<i>Divergent opinions (if any) were not taken into consideration</i>	<i>CoP; NoP</i>
Representation	Referring to the spread of representation from affected interests; including how legitimate the representation seen to be; the diversity of views not just representatives	

Criteria	Description	Application
	<i>There was a good balance among participants' categories (e.g: good ratio farmers / advisors and researcher)</i>	<i>FG; CoP; NoP</i>
	<i>Each participant had the chance to express his opinion freely</i>	<i>FG; CoP; NoP</i>
Transparency	Referring to both internal, whereby participants understand how decisions are made; and external, whereby observers can audit the process	
	<i>The rules about my involvement, on the use of my contribution and on the providing of feedbacks are clear</i>	<i>FG; CoP; NoP</i>

Impacts

Since the effect on actual uptake of IMP practices and on policy making are beyond the scope of SUPPORT, evaluation focuses refers to whether participants perceive that changes occur as a result of the participatory process; Dealing with behaviours, they are qualitative and therefore based on opinions. They are collected through likert (1-4) scales once per year.

- I.1.I feel I've given a meaningful contribution to SUPPORT activities
- I.2 I've learned something new about sustainable pest management
- I.3 Joining SUPPORT gave me the opportunity to gain new knowledge that I've applied / I'm going to apply in my profession
- I.4 SUPPORT has allowed the widening of my professional network

4.10 The Energy Timeline

The CoP events will be evaluated based on the energy timeline. It is an easy-to-use method for joint evaluation of co-creation processes. First developed for network evaluation (Wielinga, 2008), it focusses on critical moments as perceived by the participants in the session.

It involves participant in a simple yet effective exercise that allows them to describe their perception on an event (a CoP meeting, for instance) or a process (e.g.: first year of involvement in SUPPORT multi-actor platform) in a direct and easy way.

- Upper row: moments that gave energy
- Middle row: moments that took energy
- Lower row: moments of new insights or opportunities

everyone writes down the positive and negative issues. These are the factors or moments that had a positive or negative influence on the developments. Finally, everyone describes the 'light bulb'. These are the defining moments of insight when you finally 'see the light'. These moments are also placed on the timeline.

Vertical lines divide the timeline in periods with milestones that are recognisable for all. *E.g. periods in time, important events or meetings.*

When the timeline is completed, a discussion follows. This discussion allows each participant the opportunity to explain what s/he found so important in the developments and the reason. It is important to clearly be aware beforehand that each story is true. The

method is not intended to convince one another of one's own truth. There are many stories to be told. Each and every one of us has his/her own story and perception. It is can be an enlightening and surprising experience to hear how other network participants have undergone and perceived certain events. Ultimately, the discussion about this accelerates the network's learning process.

Figure 9: The energy timeline wallpaper

Source: H2020 I2Connect tools for Interactive Innovation

5. References

- Blackstock, K. L., Kelly, G. J., & Horsey, B. L. (2007). Developing and applying a framework to evaluate participatory research for sustainability. *Ecological economics*, 60(4), 726-742.
- Brzezina, N (2022) Unpadte on AKIS in Horizon Europe Cluster sic. Available from: <https://www.innovarurale.it/it/file-download/download/public/5453>;
- Bushe. G.R. (2013), Generative process, generative outcome: The transformational potential of appreciative inquiry, in D.L. Cooperrider, D.P. Zandee, L.N. Godwin, M. Avital & B. Boland (eds.) *Organizational Generativity: The Appreciative Inquiry Summit and a Scholarship of Transformation* (Advances in Appreciative Inquiry, Volume 4), Emerald Group Publishing Limited, pp.89-113;
- Castaneda DI, Toulson P. Is it possible to share tacit knowledge using information and communication technology tools? *Glob Knowledge, Mem Commun* [Internet]. 2021 Nov 16;70(8/9):673–83. Available from: <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/GKMC-07-2020-0102/full/html>;
- Catana, G.C., Debremaeker, I., Szkola, S.S.E., Williquet, F. (2021). The Communities of Practice Playbook. <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC122830>;
- Cohen D., Prusak L. (2001). *In Good Company: How Social Capital Makes Organizations Work - Making Social Capital Work*, Harvard Business Review Press, Boston, Mass;
- Cambridge, D. and Suter, V. (2005). *Community of Practice design guide: A step-by-step guide for designing & cultivating communities of practice in Higher Education*. EDUCAUSE Learning Initiative (ELI);
- Coppola M. (2008), *La comunità di pratiche online come sistema di gestione della conoscenza*, Progetto "Piano di Formazione IFEL 2008", Cittalia, Fondazione Anci Ricerche;
- Davis M. & Denning, K.(2001) Almost as helpful as good theory: Some conceptual possibilities for the online classroom, *ALT-J*, 9:2, 64-75, DOI: 10.1080/0968776010090207;
- Kumar, S., Leonard, A., Watkins, R. and Vovides, Y. (2015). *Art of Knowledge Exchange*. Washington, DC: World Bank. Retrieved from: <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/17540> ;
- Cronin E, Fieldsend A, Rogge E, Block T. Multi-actor Horizon 2020 projects in agriculture, forestry and related sectors: A Multi-level Innovation System framework (MINOS) for identifying multi-level system failures. *Agric Syst* [Internet]. 2022 Feb;196:103349. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0308521X21003024>;
- Fazey I, Bunse L, Msika J, Pinke M, Preedy K, Evelyn AC, et al. Evaluating knowledge exchange in interdisciplinary and multi-stakeholder research. *Glob Environ Chang* [Internet]. 2014 Mar;25:204–20. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0959378014000028>;
- Holzer J.M., Carmon N. and Orenstein, D.E. (2018). A methodology for evaluating transdisciplinary research on coupled socioecological systems. *Ecological Indicators*, 85: 808–819.
- Macken-Walsh, A. (2017). *Agridemo-F2F D1.8: Protocol for the Multi Actor Approach*. Available Online: https://agridemo-h2020.eu/docs/D1.8_Protocol_Multiactor_approach.pdf;
- Macken-Walsh, A. (2017) *Guidelines for Learning and Brokering Activities: SKIN project (Horizon 2020)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10485.06886>;
- Martignano, A., & Zanon, D. (2007). Il valore di una SWOT partecipata nei programmi di sviluppo locale: il caso del programma "Competitività" 2007-2013 della PA di Bolzano. In *XXVIII conferenza italiana di scienze regionali. Lo sviluppo regionale nell'Unione Europea: obiettivi Strategie, politiche*. AISRe;
- OECD (2009), "OECD DAC Glossary", in *Guidelines for Project and Programme Evaluations*, OECD, Paris, <http://www.oecd.org/development/evaluation/dcdndep/47069197.pdf>;

Rogers, C. R. (1957). The necessary and sufficient conditions of therapeutic personality change. *Journal of consulting psychology*, 21(2), 95.

Wehn, U., Gharesifard, M., Ceccaroni, L. *et al.* Impact assessment of citizen science: state of the art and guiding principles for a consolidated approach. *Sustain Sci* **16**, 1683–1699 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-021-00959-2>;

Wenger, E. (2011). Communities of practice: A brief introduction. <https://scholarsbank.uoregon.edu/xmlui/handle/1794/11736>

Wielinga, E.(2008) Encouraging sustainable innovations in animal husbandry by using the FAN approach (Free Actors in Networks);

Wielinga, E. and Robijn, S. (2020). Energising networks – Tools for co-creation. ISBN: 978-90-8686-351-8 <https://doi.org/10.3920/978-90-8686-904-6>